

Existence of Indonesian Police Performance in Facing Impact of Digital Media News

(Case Study in North Maluku Regional Police)

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ABSTRACT: The current dependence of the world's community on the internet and digital media has thickened through social media platforms (Facebook, Instagram and Twitter) which have been expanded with social media networks (WhatsApp, Line, We Chat, etc.). The impact of a digital media coverage that spreads rapidly and massively, often causes conflict and even violent conflict. Posting of status on social media walls, which leads to hatred, insults, and inappropriate words that easily provoke anger. The National Police as the guardian of law enforcement, guardian of security and public order, as well as protector, and public servant is in dire need of various breakthroughs to be able to improve its performance in responding to the impact of existing news. This study aims to describe the performance of the North Maluku Regional Police in dealing with the impact of digital media coverage. Data was collected through direct observation and recording as well as interviews with informants by referring to the interview guidelines. The sampling method was using simple random sampling technique. This research is focused on the study of performance indicators which include: first, input indicators, namely budget, human resources, equipment, policies and time; second, process indicators, namely planning, handling procedures, timeliness; and third, the results indicators, namely the level of satisfaction, the level of service quality and the accuracy of the case resolution. The results showed that the performance of the North Maluku Regional Police in terms of law enforcement in terms of input indicators, there was good performance in the aspects of budget, policy and time, and the results were less both in the aspects of human resources and equipment. Meanwhile, from the process indicator, there is a good performance in the planning aspect, the handling procedure aspect and the bad performance is found in the aspect of explaining the timeliness and the result indicator, there is a bad performance in all aspects. Meanwhile, in terms of media management, it shows that the North Maluku Regional Police has a good performance in all aspects of input indicators, process indicators and outcome indicators.

KEYWORDS– Existence of Indonesian Police Performance, Digital Media News.

I. INTRODUCTION

The world community today is faced with the fast development of communication and information technology and easily accessible with a variety of choices, which is known as the digital era. This era marked the use of conventional media to become digital media which later became a milestone in the emergence of social media platforms such as: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and others.

The use of digital media in the form of social media in the community brings various changes in various fields such as politics, economy, socio-culture, defense, security, and information technology itself (Setiawan, 2017). Also, these changes have a positive impact, including the use of digital media to expand network of friends, market goods and services, etc. Meanwhile, the negative impact is the presence of hoaxes, hate speech, and fake news.

One of the important institutions of this nation that is also affected by the development of information and communication technology is the Indonesian National Police. Along with the development of digital media and the impact of the media, it is closely related to the performance of the National Police, which of course must follow the direction of change. Maintaining conventional ways of performance that are no longer in line with the breath of information technology development (digital era) is an underdevelopment for an institution.

Throughout 2018, the National Police's performance was considered positive and the level of public trust in the police was getting better. As with the analysis of Media Intelligence Rustika Herlambang, which released the results of research on the level of neutral, negative and positive sentiment of the public towards the National Police through digital media with 100,000 internet users who post or talk about police in digital media. As a result, the public's positive sentiment towards the Police is greater this year compared to the previous year. Meanwhile, negative sentiment surged high in May 2018 during the bombing of three churches in Surabaya, East Java. The negative and neutral public sentiment towards the police institution this year tends to decrease. (Berita Satu, 2019).

In the local sphere, especially in the province of North Maluku, the National Police has shown hard work to achieve good performance. The standpoint of this study is the effectiveness of the National Police's performance in the Regional Police in dealing with the impact of social media news. The data that the authors collected was from data handled by Sub-Directorate 2 of the North Maluku Regional Police's Special Criminal Investigation Directorate (Ditreskrimsus) for January-December 2018, there were twenty incidents related to IT cases..

Departing from this background, the author is interested in examining the existence of the National Police's performance in dealing with the impact of social media, especially at the North Maluku Regional Police. This is based on the reality that the Indonesian republic police institution will be faced with the fact that the police performance challenges, both institutionally and personally, will face more severe challenges due to social media. Based on some of the conditions described earlier, the problem to be investigated is how the existence of the North Maluku Regional Police in digital media reporting and how the impact of aspects and cases of digital media news on the public and how to handle it by the North Maluku Regional Police.

Based on the description above, the research objectives are to; "**Describing the Performance of the North Maluku Regional Police in Digital Media News and the Handling Method**".

II. HEADINGS

The Existence of Organizational Performance

Existence according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI) means: being; existence. Which, when examined in depth, the word existence shows one's identity, performance, appearance, and / or tendency. Existence functions positively, namely the achievement of the expected goals, and negatively when the goals are not achieved. At this level, the existence of an institution will be seen through the performance produced by the institution, whether its performance is good or vice versa.

According to Revianto in (Masruri dan Muazanyah, 2017) The effectiveness is how great the works that had done, how people created the achievement based on their own hopes. In this case, if a work can be finishing by a plan, either time, budget, or neither the qualities, it would be said effectiveness. (Masruri and Muazansyah, 2017).

On the other hand, according to Gibson *et al.* (in Bungkaes, 2013), effectiveness is an assessment that had made related to individual, team, and organization achievements. More closed their achievements to their own hopes (standard), it would more effective in the assessment of them. (Bungkaes, 2013).

The existence is more influencing by the people's works in order to create a achievement. In English, the works can be translated as *job performance or actual performance or level of performance*, which is the level of success of the employee in completing the given job. Performance is a manifestation of the ability in the form of real work or is the result of work achieved by employees in carrying out tasks and jobs that come from the company. (Priansa, 2017). On the other hand, according to Colquitt, LePine, and Wesson (Wahyurudhanto, 2018), A work is "*The value of the set of employee behaviors that contribute, either positively or negatively, to organizational goal accomplishment*". Nilai dari seperangkat perilaku karyawan yang berkontribusi, baik secara positif atau negatif terhadap pemenuhan tujuan organisasi)

The Role of the Indonesian National Police

The Police of the Republic of Indonesia as a government institution with a position directly below the President, are required to present a good performance. According to Article 5 paragraph (1) of Law no. 2 of 2002: "The National Police of the Republic of Indonesia is an instrument of the state that plays a role in maintaining security and public order, upholding the law, and providing protection and services to the community in the context of maintaining domestic security".

In the provisions of the Law, there are two fundamental tasks of the National Police as stated in Tribrata and Catur Prasetya Polri. As regulated in Law no. 2 of 2002, especially in Article 13. In the provisions of Article 13 it is emphasized that the Police have the following duties:

- a. maintaining security and public order;
- b. enforcing the law; and
- c. providing services and protection to the community.

Departing from the above definition, the Indonesian National Police referred to in this study refers more to the institution, the police institution that will be the unit of analysis, namely the North Maluku Regional Police, which is basically at the Directorate of Special Criminals (Ditreskrimsus) of the North Maluku Regional Police and the Public Relations Division (Bidhumas).) North Maluku Regional Police.

Impact of Digital Media News with Social Media Platforms

Digital Media as usually associated as a new media. According to Carey in (McQuail, 2011) New Media is a media that used the advance bases devices were computer and mobilephone. These main power that has changes as the first time is satellite communication and used the computer devices. The keyword of great power the computer devices as communication tools is put on the digitalize process that could brought to the all informations tools form more in easier and efficiency. (Mc.Quail, 2011).

One of the platforms for digital media is social media. Social media according to Puntoadi (2011: 1) is a website-based feature that can form networks and allow people to interact in a community. On social media, we can carry out various forms of exchange, collaboration and get to know each other in the form of visual writing and audio-visual. Examples such as twitter, facebook, blog, forsquare and others (Puntoadi, 2011).

The use of social media in the social sector according to Power and Philips-Waren (2012) (in Rustiana, 2018), namely: first, social media is a tool to improve connectivity between two or more people / groups / organizations. Second, social media creates new forms of friendship in a wider and faster scope than face-to-face contexts. Third, social media can encourage large numbers of people or mobilize society with fatal consequences or other negative influences. Fourth. social networking as a "saturation" effect that has an impact on making unwise decisions. The "saturation" effect refers to the communication overload experienced by members of a communication network group because a person can have more than five social network groups (Rustiana, 2018).

The negative impact of social media according to Siddiqui and Singh (2016) (in Rustiana, 2018) is first, to make people addicted. People spend too much time on social networking sites which can distract from their concentration and focus from certain tasks. Second, social media can easily influence the behavior of children and adolescents because sometimes people share photos and videos on media that contain violence and negative things. Third, the abuse of social media use by a group of people by invading people's privacy (Rustiana, 2018).

To emphasize the influence of digital media reporting on social media platforms, as illustrated by the various views above. So this research is directed to see, examine and examine the extent of the influence of digital media on the performance of the North Maluku Regional Police.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a qualitative approach with the type of case study research to determine the existence of the police's institutional performance in understanding the impact of digital media through social media platforms. Case studies can be used to fulfill personal interests because of their interest in a particular problem, and not to build a particular theory (Raharjo, 2017). This research was conducted at the North Maluku Regional Police, adjusted to the information / data needs required, namely the Special Criminal Investigation Directorate (Ditreskrimsus), the Public Relations Division of the North Maluku Regional Police and Online Media Managers as well as victims / families of a crime. The time of conducting the research was adjusted to the readiness of the informants to be asked for information.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact of Aspects and Cases of Digital Media Coverage and Handling Methods by the North Maluku Regional Police

There are several cases that occurred in the jurisdiction of the North Maluku Regional Police which influenced public opinion and contributed to the performance of the North Maluku Regional Police in the view of the public, especially in the field of law enforcement and media management, as listed in the table below:

Table 1. Public Opinion and the Impact of Digital Media Coverage at the North Maluku Regional Police in 2018-2019

No	Public Opinion	Impact of News
1	2	3
A	Year 2018	
1	The opinion of the North Maluku Regional Police is considered not neutral in the holding of the Regional Head Election for the Governor / Deputy Governor of North Maluku Province by the Indonesian Pilkada Observer Movement (GPPI), in August 2018.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The independence of Polda's legitimacy was questioned; ▪ Public trust in the North Maluku police has gradually diminished.
B	Year 2019	
2	The mass Christianization opinion conducted by the Barokah Barokah Surya Nusantara (YBSN) Foundation to elementary, junior and senior high school students in Morotai Regency. Opinion distribution via Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram and Twitter in February 2019.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sparked the anger of activists and Islamic religious figures as well as the community and MUI which was conveyed in the demonstration; ▪ The news was carried out massively through the social media Facebook and WhatsApp; ▪ Report to Ditreskrimsus Polda Malut to handle the case.
3	Opinion Indication 2 (two) female police personnel of the North Maluku Regional Police were exposed to radical ideology and were recruited as part of a radical / terrorism group.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The spread of negative Polda news through social media (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and WhatsApp) The North Maluku Regional Police are considered negligent in conducting personnel development.
4	The insulting opinion of the Prophet Muhammad SAW by the owner of the Facebook account Michael Ratulangi, in December 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ This sparked the anger of activists and Islamic religious figures and the community who were conveyed via social media Facebook, WhatsApp and Twitter, and then the case was reported to the Malut Regional Police's Ditreskrimsus to be handled.

Source: Informan, 2020 (edited)

Based on the data sources in table 1. above, the impact of digital media coverage on the North Maluku Regional Police as a consequence of public attention to the police can be described as follows:

a. Positive Impact.

Below are some of the positive impacts:

- 1) The North Maluku Regional Police Institution can access various information about an incident, both criminal and non-criminal, live and non-live from written statements and videos of social media users.
- 2) The North Maluku Regional Police Institution can find out various criticisms, complaints or disappointments, either directly or indirectly from written statements or videos of social media users regarding the performance of the National Police.

- 3) The North Maluku Regional Police Institution can find out various suggestions and input from various written posts of social media users.
- 4) The North Maluku Regional Police Institution can build good cooperation with various communities and social media activists and online media.
- 5) The North Maluku Regional Police Institute can access various information and news related to developments in regional, national and international situations that are posted or shared by the community or social media activists.
- 6) Digital media news coverage encourages the North Maluku Regional Police to improve law enforcement and improve media management in a professional, transparent and accountable manner.
- 7) Digital media coverage can be a reference in taking future police leadership policies, addressing the dynamics of problems that occur with high intensity and speed.
- 8) Digital media news coverage is a driving force in making massive and integrated improvements to create a professional, modern and reliable police department.
- 9) The National Police is able to obtain information on the location of the suspected perpetrators of crime quickly through information submitted from users or social media activists.
- 10) Digital media (social media) is a medium of communication between leaders and subordinates as well as between divisions within the North Maluku Regional Police.

b. Negative Impact.

Below are some of the negative impacts:

- 1) The increasing number of criminal acts in the form of insults, defamation, fraud, and statements that are disturbing many people, as well as false statements or fraudulent.
- 2) Increased number of ITE crimes using social media which causes the burden of handling investigations and investigations into ITE criminal cases to increase.
- 3) Uncontrolled negative response to the performance of the North Maluku Regional Police, published directly by social media users without confirming its liability.
- 4) This creates a high level of antipathy towards the North Maluku Regional Police, if there is negative information regarding the actions of police officers who violate rules, legal norms or take actions that damage the image of the police department.
- 5) Circulation and the spread of hatespeech directly or hoaxes without being controlled by the police institution, causing worry or panic in the midst of society or riots between community groups.
- 6) The burden of restoring or rebuilding the image of the National Police, which has already fallen, is taking a long time, which must be done immediately through anticipatory steps and improvements through measured media management.
- 7) The development of new modes of crime published freely through social media, resulting in the emergence of similar crimes. So that criminal acts are increasingly happening.
- 8) Encouraging or triggering demonstrations from related parties that highlight issues or public opinion related to the news that occurred.

Regarding the impact of digital media coverage described in the table above, the North Maluku Regional Police are looking for a solution for both law enforcement and media management carried out by Ditreskrim Polda Maluku Utara and Bidhumas Polda North Maluku in this research, described in the table below, as follows:

Table. 2. Efforts in Facing the Impact of Digital Media News Coverage At the North Maluku Regional Police in 2018-2019

No	Public Opinion	The efforts of the North Maluku Regional Police	Achieved Result
1	2	3	4
A	Year 2018		
1	The opinion of the North Maluku Regional Police is considered not neutral in the holding of the Regional Head Election for the Governor / Deputy Governor of Prov. North Maluku by the Indonesian Pilkada Observer Movement (GPPI), in August 2018.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Making a press release to straighten out news related to GPPI's points of complaint through printed media, online media and social media; ▪ Carrying out an open dialogue with the stakeholders to restore public trust. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The community remains calm and the Kamtibmas situation is safe and conducive; ▪ The North Maluku public appreciates the effort of enforcing the law of the North Maluku Regional Police.
B	Year 2019		
2	The mass Christianization opinion conducted by the Barokah Barokah Surya Nusantara Foundation (YBSN) to elementary, junior and senior high school students in the district. Morotai. Opinion distribution via Facebook, WhatsApp, and Instagram and twitter. In February 2019.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Making a press release explaining the efforts to enforce the law against the suspect through print media, online media and social media carried out by the North Maluku Regional Police as an effort to create social security. ▪ Conducting an open dialogue with stakeholders to overcome public anger. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The community remains calm and the Kamtibmas situation is safe and conducive; ▪ The North Maluku public appreciates the effort of enforcing the law of the North Maluku Regional Police.
3	Opinion Indication 2 (two) female police personnel of the North Maluku Regional Police were exposed to radical ideology and were recruited as part of a radical / terrorism group.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Releasing news explaining the real problems and legal efforts made by the North Maluku Regional Police through printed media, online media and social media. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Negative opinion is gradually decreasing and finally stopped ; ▪ The public becomes more aware of the dangers of radical group doctrine.
4	The insulting opinion of the Prophet Muhammad SAW by the owner of the Facebook account Michael Ratulangi, in December 2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Releasing news to explain the law enforcement efforts against the suspect through print media, online media and social media carried out by the North Maluku Regional Police as an effort to create security and peace. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The community remains calm and the Kamtibmas situation is safe and conducive; ▪ The North Maluku public appreciates the effort of enforcing the law of the North Maluku Regional Police.

Source: Informant, 2020 (edited)

Based on the data sources in table 2. above, the handling strategy of the North Maluku Regional Police in dealing with the impact of digital media news coverage from the aspects of law enforcement and media management can be concluded as follows:

a. Law Enforcement Aspect.

- 1) Receive complaints from victims / families in the form of police reports in the "B" model and make police reports on "A" models for criminal incidents that are directly discovered by the investigator / assistant investigator.
- 2) Conducting media releases related to criminal events that have occurred and law enforcement measures that should be taken.
- 3) Conducting criminal investigations that have occurred and are reported to the National Police in a professional, transparent and accountable manner.
- 4) Delivering the progress of the investigation results to the victim / family.
- 5) Complete criminal investigations quickly so that the case files, suspects and evidence are immediately submitted to the Prosecutor's Office (Public Prosecutor).

b. Media Management Aspect.

- 1) Conducting media releases by the unit in responding to public opinion that occurs in the form of police actions taken as well as clarification of the news.
- 2) Conducting media releases related to police measures taken preemptively, preventively, and repressively to the public in an open manner.
- 3) Conducting an open dialogue with stake holders in order to solve the occurring problems so that they do not cause an impact or causing disruption of social security.
- 4) Monitoring various news reports through online media and through social media to respond and determine future actions of the police and the policies of the National Police leadership.
- 5) Publicize the success of the National Police in upholding the law, and creating Harkamtibmas, as well as protection, and community services.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results that have been described above, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Whereas the performance profile of the North Maluku Regional Police in facing digital media coverage in law enforcement is seen from the results indicators showing poor performance in the aspects of the level of satisfaction, the level of service quality and the accuracy of solving cases submitted to the Prosecutor's Office. Meanwhile, media management aspect shows good performance in the aspects of service quality and satisfaction levels.
2. Whereas the impact and handling of digital media coverage on the performance of the North Maluku Regional Police can be positive, if in carrying out their duties and responsibilities of law enforcement and media management, officers can be open and quickly respond to critical issues that occur in a professional, transparent and accountable manner. On the contrary, it is negative if the police action violates the prevailing laws and regulations and is not in line with the established standard operating procedures and ignores public opinion.

REFERENCES

- [1] Setiawan, Wawan. (2017), "*Era Digital dan Tantangannya*", makalah pada Seminar Nasional Pendidikan 2017.
- [2] Berita satu. (2019). Kinerja Polri Selama 2018, Survey Masyarakat. (<https://www.beritasatu.com/nasional/529833/kinerja-polri-selama-2018-urvei-masyarakat-lebih-percaya, akses 12/04/2019>).
- [3] Masruri dan Muazansyah, I. (2017). Analisis Efektivitas Program Nasional Pemberdayaan Masyarakat Mandiri Perkotaan (PNPM) (Studi Kasus Pada Kecamatan Banyu Kabupaten Bulungan Tahun 2010). *Journal Goovernance and Public Policy*. 4(2):363-393.
- [4] Bungkaes H.R, J. H. Posumah, dan Burhanuddin Kiyai. (2013). Hubungan Efektifitas Pengelolaan Program Raskin dengan Peningkatan Kesejahteraan Masyarakat di Desa Manahan Kecamatan Gemeh Kabupaten Kepulauan Talaud. *Journal Acta Diurna*, 2(2):1-23.
- [5] Penerbit Pustaka Setia, Priansa, Donni Juni. Manajemen Kinerja Kepegawaian dalam Pengelolaan SDM Perusahaan. (Bandung, 2017).
- [6] Wahyurudhanto, W. (2018). Kepuasan Masyarakat Terhadap Kinerja Polri. *Journal Ilmu Kepolisian*. 12 (3): 2621-8410.
- [7] McQuail, Denis. *Teori Komunikasi Massa* McQuail. Edisi 6 Buku 1. (Salemba Humanika, Jakarta, 2011).
- [8] Puntodi, Denis. *Menciptakan Penjualan Melalui Media Sosial*. (Jakarta. PT. Elex Komputindo, 2011).
- [9] Rustiana. (2018). Persepsi Digital Dependent terhadap Pemanfaatan Media Sosial dan Dampak Sosial Ekonomi. *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi*. 15 (1): 17-32.
- [10] Rahardjo, Mudjia. "*Studi Kasus dalam Penelitian Kualitatif : Konsep dan Prosedurnya*," Kertas Kerja, Program Pascasarjana., Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim, Malang, 2017.